

Statistical, Correlational, and Network Analyses of Top-Selling Video Games on a Game Store

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Abstract—In recent years, the video game industry has seen significant growth, leading to an increased interest in understanding market trends and consumer preferences. The aim of this study is to analyze over 5,000 video games released on Steam in 2024 to identify statistical and behavioral patterns across top-performing titles. To achieve this, the study utilized data from third-party aggregators and examine the variables using various analytical techniques. Descriptive statistics, Pearson R, and Network Analysis was employed to see the unseen in the dataset. The study revealed that follower count and price showed moderate correlations, and hobbyist and indie games displayed greater variability in performance. On the other hand, tags and genres network map further highlighted popular theme combinations that contributed to success. The findings of the study suggest practical implications for developers seeking to optimize their market strategies, and to provide a deeper understanding of genre dynamics and consumer interests in an increasingly saturated market.

Keywords—video games, game tags, game genres, network analysis, game development, Steam, correlation

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

Video games have become a staple in the 21st century, so much so that [1] declared in their book that they are becoming a central part of cultural lives, influencing many aspects of life, such as consumption, communities, and identity formation. With top-selling titles generating billions of dollars, it is not a surprise that video games are deeply rooted in the society of today and exert influence across generations, regardless of age. Reference [2] claimed that games bring a wide range of benefits including being an effective educational tool, especially regarding cultural aspects, and an instrument of triggering positive emotion in players (e.g., joy, satisfaction, and enthusiasm, and imparting values and encourage empathy through the characters and their

circumstances. These games are not just simple pastimes but complex products that reflect the creativity, market strategy, problem-solving, and technological innovation of the team behind them and their player base.

Studying these games using their sales, publisher class, and inherent properties like tags and genre will reveal patterns that influence consumer interest and the decisions of developers and publishers. This is especially significant in this era, where the market is no longer dominated by AAA studios. Smaller developers, such as indie and hobbyists, are now producing successful and influential titles, as seen from their revenues competing with big studios [3]. Therefore, a thorough investigation can offer insight into the evolution of the industry and the tastes of consumers. By extracting connections between these elements and market results, the study seeks to offer valuable insights for developers, publishers, and scholars interested in understanding the changing dynamics of video game success in an increasingly diverse and unrelenting industry.

B. Objectives of the Study

The study aims to analyze over 5000 video games released in 2024 from the digital marketplace Steam based on relevant metrics, including revenue, sold copies, price, Steam followers, release date, early access, publisher class, developers, and tags used. The objectives and findings expected from this study include the following:

- 1) Perform basic statistical analysis on numerical variables in the dataset
- 2) Examine the relationship between variables
- 3) Identify the combination of tags and genres most used by the best-selling games, and the publisher class.

C. Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study includes over 5000 video games, which were gathered from third-party sites GameDiscoverCo and Gamalytic. The data sheet retrieved from the list of Over Powered Game Marketing (OPGM) includes: Game Header, Game Title, Steam Link, Revenue, Copies Sold, Price, Steam

Followers, Release Date, Video Game Early Access, Publisher Class, Publishers, Developers, and Tags. This dataset provides a clear and concise full picture of video game sales, analyzing market trends between Double-A, Indie Game, and Hobbyist Classification for over 5000 games included in the OPGM list. Furthermore, the researchers also included the genres through the Steam Game Store.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. *Video Games, Tags, and Genre*

Video games, as stated by [4] are digital forms of interactive entertainment that place the player in alternate worlds governed by alien principles and constraints, something that goes beyond reality. They are a medium that reflects a mix of creative expression if it aims for something beautiful, entertainment if the goal is to make money, playthings if they boast an interactive design, challenge if there are goals to be achieved, and conflict if there exist competitors [5]. Since their inception as simple pixel-based activities to the complex worldbuilding and story-driven games of today, video games have become one of the most culturally, socially, and economically significant media forms. [6]. So much so that their purpose now transcends their initial essence, that is, to bring enjoyment to the players, as they can now provide positive cognitive, motivational, emotional, and social influences [7]. Studies have also shown that games can enhance learning and collaboration, as seen in the study of [8], and all of these applications highlight the growing importance of video games in modern society.

Video games can be classified into genres, which help players understand at a glance what kind of challenges and experiences a game will offer [9]. As an example, a video game with an adventure genre emphasizes story, exploration, solving puzzles, and inventory management over action, while an action genre offers a fast-paced gameplay focus on combat that tests the reflexes and hand-eye coordination of the players [9]. Other video game genres include sports, simulation, platformer, role-playing games (RPG), first-person shooter (FPS), and racing. Another way to categorize a video game is through tags. Tags are more specific descriptors that include features, themes, or gameplay elements, which help users quickly learn about the game [10]. Steam tags can involve sub-genres, visuals and viewpoints, themes and moods, features, and players, to name a few [10]. They both play a significant role in the gaming industry, with games being published left and right. Genres, according to [9], give players a general idea of the characteristics of a game that match their tastes; meanwhile, tags, according to [10], are refined filtering tools that help narrow down games beyond

broad categorization offered by genre in the highly diverse gaming market.

B. *Game Development Methods, Budgets, Pricing, and Classification*

As gaming grew to one of the largest entertainment juggernauts of the contemporary industry, beating out the music and movie industry [11], there came a gold rush from the newfound disposable income proving gaming resilient to economic shocks of the modern world due to their flexible nature of purchase, acquisition, and elevation of gaming experience through microtransactions, gacha mechanics, in-game ads, and much more [12].

To understand the underlying assumption between the game classification, a baseline must be made on what constitutes and qualifies as a AAA, AA, and an Indie game. This baseline references funding and investment with a particular focus on their pricing. [13]. Indie game publishers must have made more than \$10 thousand to less than \$50 million, costing below \$30, with an estimated median price of \$19.99. Meanwhile, AA game publishers must have published at least two games, made more than \$50 million to less than \$500 million lifetime revenue, and at least \$10 million average revenue per game, costing around \$29.99–\$39.99. Lastly, AAA game publishers must have published at least two games and made more than \$500 million lifetime revenue, with at least \$10 million average revenue per game released, costing around \$60 or higher [13].

There are multiple ways aside from full-cost consumer purchase that game developers can use to further monetize the gaming experience, which has led to it becoming the largest entertainment industry. Reference [14] examined the hurdle game developers use to overcome the monetization challenge in freemium online games, which are also creeping into non-free games and the social implication through a measure of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the service provider, examining the moderating role of achievement and social orientation of players, which may encourage achievement-oriented players to pay while socially-oriented players are in diametrical opposition.

In a study conducted by [15], the researcher examined how game critique impacts game design decisions, including a case study of monetization and loot boxes—a raffle-like slot machine for virtual goods on a tier-based rarity and importance matrix. It emphasizes the role of game critique in the public perception of game design decisions, which shape gaming cultures and the consumption and production of the commodity. A study conducted by [16] also examined the reaction of gaming consumers to the use of controversial Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) in its

heyday in AAA Video Games, showing a negative inclination in crypto tokens from the gaming community.

III. METHODOLOGY

The numeric data will be treated using basic statistical concepts, such as the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum, which follow the methodology used in the study of [17]. This enabled them to find patterns in the data, such as all their numeric variables (e.g., number of languages, storage requirements, price) are skewed heavily toward zero.

$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$	x = Observations given n = Total number of observations
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Image 1: Mean Formula [18]

If n is odd, then $M = \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)^{\text{th}} \text{ term}$ If n is even, then $M = \frac{\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)^{\text{th}} \text{ term} + \left(\frac{n}{2} + 1\right)^{\text{th}} \text{ term}}{2}$	n = Total number of observations
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Image 2: Median Formula [18]

$S = \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n}}$	x = Observations given \bar{x} = Mean n = Total number of observations
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Image 3: Standard Deviation Formula [18]

The researchers will also employ the Pearson R to discover associations between two variables (x and y). In this study, it could be used to find if there exist relations between price and followers, revenue and followers, and followers and copies sold, to name a few.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Image 4: Pearson R Formula [19]

A network analysis will also be implemented in the tags and genre, which mimics the methods used by [17] in their 2021 study. They created a web-like structure (shown in Image 5) composed of nodes and edges, representing genres and games, respectively. This method gives them insight into which genres are popular and how interconnected each genre is to the categories. This suits the objective of the study, which aims to find what tags and genres are used by the top-selling Steam games of 2024. Another analytical method that could be used is clustering to group similar games based on certain criteria.

Image 5: Network Plot of [17]

These methods, along with the tools to be used (e.g., Python and Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis [WEKA]) will subject the data to a rigorous treatment that will shed light on some patterns that may not be visible using the eye test alone.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Basic Statistical Concepts

TABLE I. Summary of Results for the Numerical Variables

	Mean	Median	Mode
Revenue	\$354,000.00	\$5,509.00	\$575.00
Copies Sold	33,122.94	865.5	146
Price	\$14.04	\$9.99	\$9.99
Steam Followers	3,104.80	328	66

TABLE II. Summary of Results for the Numerical Variables (Cont.)

	Standard Deviation	Max	Min
Revenue	\$3,792,676.68	\$133,864,019.00	\$500.00
Copies Sold	578442.44	40,795,059	15
Price	\$20.48	\$199.00	\$0.00
Steam Followers	14,712.67	491,152	1

There are 5772 video games included in the 2024 Video Games Steam Catalogue of Over OPGM, with revenues ranging from \$500 to ~\$134 million. The sum of all revenues generated amounted to \$2,047,401,126.86, the mean or average revenue for video games released on Steam is \$354,000 for each game, with a median revenue of \$5,509 and a most recurring revenue figure at \$575. The standard deviation with the highest revenue value recorded to be at around \$133 million and the lowest value recorded in the dataset pegged at \$500 reaches a staggering and highly varied interval of deviation at \$3,792,676.68. This captures the staggering revenue variability over the distributed 5000+ video games in the dataset while also indicating a large disparity between the top 1,000 grossing video games and the rest of the data collected. There exists a great variability among the values, where only a few games truly became hits in the gaming industry, earning huge

revenues and gathering massive followers, leaving most games behind.

B. Variable Relationships

Table III: Pearson Coefficient Correlation

Variable Relationship	Pearson R Value	Interpretation
Followers & Price	0.08	Weak Correlation
Followers & Revenue	0.74	Strong (Positive) Correlation
Followers & Copies Sold	0.1	Weak Correlation
Price & Revenue	0.06	Weak Correlation
Price & Copies Sold	-0.04	Weak Correlation

The researchers used Pearson-R Coefficient of Correlation to examine the variable relationships between select numbers of factors with mostly weak correlation between factors except regarding Followers & Revenue which resulted in a Strong Positive Correlation.

Image 6: Publisher Class (x-axis) vs Revenue (y-axis)

For the publisher class and revenue, the correlation coefficient was not used to determine their association since one value is nominal (publisher class) while the other is numerical (revenue). However, there are stark differences between the three, as seen from the graph. AA publishers have the least number of games released in 2024, followed by Hobbyist, while Indie has the most games. However, the highest-selling games are published by AA developers and publishers, which is supported by a total revenue of \$1.1 billion and an average revenue of \$5.5 million. In contrast, Indie, which has the most games, only has \$934 million in total revenue with an average of \$279 thousand per title. Both of which are lower than what the AA game developers have. This means that AA companies have produced more successful games in the market than Indie and Hobbyist game developers. These pieces of data show the relationship between publisher class and revenue, where the more commercially backed a game is, the higher its success in the gaming market.

C. Network Analysis

Image 7: Network Plot of Tags and Genre

After careful processing of the dataset, the researchers were able to narrow down the top 100 combinations of tags and genres that have been the most popular and seen throughout the entirety of the different games presented. The network graph presented in image 6 shows the tags/genre as nodes, where the size indicates how many games have that tag/genre, and the connections between these tags (known as edges) are the games that possess those two tags, where its thickness shows how many games contain that exact combination of tags.

Table IV. Top 20 Tag/Genre Combination

Tags/Genre Combination		Quantity
Indie	Singleplayer	2288
Adventure	Singleplayer	2095
Casual	Singleplayer	1883
2D	Singleplayer	1772
Action	Singleplayer	1607
3D	Singleplayer	1510
Simulation	Singleplayer	1250
Singleplayer	Story Rich	1220
Casual	Indie	1165
Action	Adventure	1125
Atmospheric	Singleplayer	1122
Adventure	Indie	1110
Exploration	Singleplayer	1078
Adventure	Exploration	1068
Cute	Singleplayer	1048
RPG	Singleplayer	1031
2D	Casual	1026
2D	Indie	997
Adventure	Story Rich	990

From the data presented in Table 4, the singleplayer category is, by far, the most played type of game in the market, but this does not come as a surprise, as a majority of games are built for one player only, so that much is understandable. The other popular tags/genres are adventure, casual, and action. Adventure is a nice

and common tag for a lot of games, especially since games surrounding adventure bring the players new things to look forward to within a fictional world, which is one of the reasons why story rich is also up there, as good stories truly do sell. Casual makes sense to also be favored in games, as they provide accessible gameplay to a wide variety of players. Furthermore, casual games give gamers something to do for a moment without having to be locked into whatever game they decide to play, making it fun regardless of location, home or outside, and device, a personal computer or smartphone. When developers want to grab attention, action is one of the top choices, as it is thrilling to watch and experience, which is why the craziest of games that have multiple things happening simultaneously can nab the taste of many wanting to look for something fun to do. As for other tags, 2D and 3D are more of a stylistic choice by developers. Now, numerous developers have started to transcend the limits, wherein countless games are becoming more 3D in art style to follow the trends of newer games. However, 2D can still capture the hearts of many. Both have charms of their own, which appeal to different users. A surprising tag is Indie, as it is not in the top 10 of the most popular tags/genres, but is included in three of the top 20 combinations of tags/genres.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

The video game industry has grown rapidly, so much so that video games are now widespread, leading to a 75% chance of at least one member of a household playing games [20]. What once was considered something for children has now become so ubiquitous that people across all ages engage in this activity [21]. As video games become increasingly central to many lives, it is crucial to analyze the gaming industry, that is, how developers of different classes (e.g., AA, Indie, and Hobbyist) and preferences of gamers interact, which is reflected in the top-selling video games in the market. This study revealed the top-heaviness of the 2024 Steam video games in terms of revenue, wherein the average earning of a game is highly inflated by the top-performing titles, indicated by the enormous gap between the revenue mean, median, and mode, as well as the immense deviation of nearly \$3.8 million. Correlation analyses show that price, followers, copies sold, and revenue are weakly or inconsistently associated, except for a modest positive correlation between revenue and followers. This highlights the importance of a community that increases the reach and popularity of games among the masses. Remarkably, AA publishers, despite releasing fewer

titles in 2024, have the most highly profitable games, underscoring the advantage of a team with a reputation and an established space in the market, leading to a higher chance of success in the gaming space over Indie and Hobbyist developers.

Regarding the nature of video games, singleplayer, adventure, casual, and story-rich tags/genres dominated the lists. This displays the taste of players for accessible games with an immersive experience. Moreover, simulation and exploration types of games have a strong footing in the gaming industry. In terms of artistic decisions made by developers, the network analysis shows that 3D games are on the rise, while 2D art style is still well-liked by the masses. Overall, the findings emphasize the highly competitive yet unpredictable nature of the Steam gaming market, where the success of games relies not only on pricing or production value but also on community engagement and tags/genre alignment with market trends.

B. Recommendation

The study has found fascinating discoveries based on the information gathered regarding how diverse the gaming industry really is, which made it difficult to find the reason for the performance of a game. While the findings give some possible grounds for this issue, they did not cover all facets to provide a sound and complete resolution as to what exactly drives success for these games. A recommendation would be to dive deeper into the inner workings of the main genres that seem to best resonate with the consumers, which would be helpful for game developers, regardless of class, wanting to make the next top-selling game. A proper understanding of the different genres, their associated mechanics and gameplays, and how to successfully implement them is key, especially when grabbing the attention of potential markets. It would also be an invaluable addition to the analysis of video games (i.e., statistical analysis and correlation) to include genres in conjunction with user-generated tags, as this research only relied on the existing genres within the tags.

On the other hand, it is essential to note that the data is from released games in 2024, and the conclusion cannot be applied to other years, as various external factors present in that year that affected the people, their decisions, and market could have influenced the data or skew it one way or another. Therefore, future research about the matter could attempt to be more inclusive with their dataset, broadening the scope of the study to include older games as well, to create more generalized findings.

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